

GraphAfghanica: Building a Federated Knowledge Infrastructure for Afghan Historical Images

This project aims to connect digital archives containing extensive collections of photographs taken in Afghanistan during the 1970s, a decade marked by profound socio-political transformation, from a society moving toward modernization to one increasingly destabilized by conflict. The project focuses on two significant collections of historical Afghan imagery.

The first is the **Bibliotheca Afghanica (BA)** at Basel University Library, which comprises nearly 150,000 photographs depicting Afghan landscapes, people, cities, architecture, and cultural life [1]. Bequeathed to the Basel University Library in 2023, the BA includes approximately 33,000 images taken during the 1970s. Today, it is one of the most comprehensive collections of Afghan historical photography worldwide; the *British Museum Magazine* (Autumn 2025) recently described it as likely the largest accessible archive of historical photographs of Afghanistan.

The second is the **EWA-76 collection**, consisting of roughly 1,500 photographs produced during the Polish ethnological Asian expedition conducted in the summer of 1976 by researchers from Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań. In the 1980s, 106 black-and-white photographs from this expedition were donated to the BA by expedition member Marek Gawęcki to facilitate broader cultural exchange across the Iron Curtain. The remaining 1,038 black-and-white and 348 color photographs are preserved in the Józef Burszta Digital Archive [2]. The 1976 expedition was one of the most significant Polish ethnographic projects of the communist era, documenting agriculture, rural life, craftsmanship, bazaars, architecture, village planning, traditional medicine, and the role of women. In addition to photographs, the project produced films and hundreds of audio-recorded interviews.

Historical photographs of Afghanistan are dispersed across global institutions, private collections, and locally maintained archives. The BA and EWA-76 holdings represent only two fragments of a broader and fragmented visual record that reflects the region's complex history. While these images constitute a vital component of Afghanistan's visual memory, they often remain inaccessible, inconsistently described, and disconnected from their contexts of creation and circulation. This project, therefore, proposes a digital humanities framework for connecting such materials through a knowledge graph (KG) that integrates metadata, image content, and cross-repository relationships. Our approach connects archives without centralizing data, allowing institutions to retain complete control of their collections [3]. Although our initial focus is on the BA and EWA-76 collections, the project's framework and methodology will be developed in a generalizable manner to support future integration of additional photographic archives.

A dedicated web application will serve as the primary access point for scholars and the public, enabling queries across the distributed network and retrieval of images and associated metadata (see Figure 1). The application will rely on a RESTful API to access the KG stored in a triplestore and retrieve images from participating repositories asynchronously. To construct the RDF-based KG, we will define a provenance-aware ontology that can represent, for each image, its metadata, content, geospatial coordinates, URLs, and provenance [4]. This open-source ontology will employ the constructs of existing ontologies, such as Dublin Core [5], PROV-O [6], and schema [7], and will define new constructs to represent project-specific data. While the EWA-76 photographs in the Józef Burszta Digital Archive provide only basic metadata (photographer, date, location), the 106 photographs donated to the BA include richer metadata, including precise geospatial coordinates and multilingual descriptions. We will extract and preprocess all available metadata from both collections to construct the initial KG in accordance with the ontology.

Figure 1: Asynchronous data and image retrieval infrastructure

To enrich the representation of image content, we will develop pattern-recognition tools to classify images into four main groups: landscape, urban areas, people, and women. For this purpose, we will train a three-stage classifier using PyTorch [8]. The first stage will identify the scene type (landscape, urban, mixed/other). The second will detect whether an image contains people. The third, applied only to images containing people, will estimate whether women are visually present. The classification results will be added to each image node in the KG, enabling researchers to identify and compare images belonging to the same categories. This functionality will facilitate case studies on historical change; for example, examining how women’s appearance and presence in public spaces changed over time, or analyzing the transformation of specific urban areas such as Kabul’s bazaar before and after the onset of war. To support these kinds of studies, the platform will include an interactive timeline tool that generates chronologically ordered image sequences based on user-defined search criteria [9].

Another component of the project focuses on identifying visually similar images, including duplicates, cropped versions, or photographs capturing the same scene with minimal spectral or camera-angle variation [10]. We will develop a two-step pipeline combining fast candidate detection with precise verification. For robust similarity detection, we will use PyTorch with a pretrained ResNet-50 model [11] to extract image embeddings and compare them using cosine similarity. Image pairs identified as similar will be connected within the KG.

For images lacking content descriptions, we will generate short, neutral, multilingual descriptions (French, English, German) by combining existing metadata with visual features extracted by classifiers and processed with large language models such as Llama. To mitigate hallucination risks, we will employ a GraphRAG approach that grounds textual descriptions in the KG [12]. All automatically generated descriptions will include explicit provenance and confidence scores and will be reviewed and, if necessary, corrected by collaborating experts.

By linking distributed visual archives and augmenting them with transparent, interpretable computational methods, this project seeks to deepen global understanding of Afghanistan’s cultural heritage while supporting local custodianship and scholarly engagement. The resulting multimodal KG will serve not only as a research infrastructure but also as a platform that offers a big-picture view of Afghanistan during its most transformational times. Integrating the hundreds of interviews recorded during EWA-76, along with the expedition’s films and written reports, into this infrastructure will be considered as a subsequent project aimed at linking these rich ethnographic materials with the corresponding photographic evidence. Incorporating these multimodal sources will provide researchers with a more holistic and contextually grounded understanding of the images, enabling deeper analysis of cultural practices, social dynamics, and historical conditions documented during the expedition.

References:

- [1] Bibliotheca Afghonica, see <https://ub.unibas.ch/de/sammlungen/bibliotheca-afghonica/>.
- [2] Józef Burszta Digital Archive, see <http://cyfrowearchiwum.amu.edu.pl/archive>.
- [3] Alassi, Sepideh (2025). Leveraging Federated Search and Data Annotation for Enhanced Analysis of Biography Networks and Network Biographies. *Graphs and Networks (GNC2025)*, Mendrisio, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17249630>.
- [4] Ammann, Nora, and Alassi, Sepideh (2024) "JourneyStar: A Generic RDF-star-based Ontology for Travel Data Representation", *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 10(1), pp. 48–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.23>.
- [5] Dublin Core Ontology, <https://www.dublincore.org/resources/glossary/ontology/>
- [6] Prov Ontology, <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>.
- [7] schema Ontology, <https://schema.org/>.
- [8] Xiaogang Wang (2016), "Deep Learning in Object Recognition, Detection, and Segmentation", *Foundations and Trends® in Signal Processing: Vol. 8: No. 4*, pp 217-382. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/20000000071>.
- [9] Alassi, Sepideh (2024) "Interactive Visualization of Linked Open Data Networks Representing Historical Writings", in *Historical Network Research 2024*. Lausanne, Switzerland. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12598807>.
- [10] Srivastava, S., Divekar, A.V., Anilkumar, C. *et al.* Comparative analysis of deep learning image detection algorithms. *J Big Data* 8, 66 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-021-00434-w>.
- [11] What is ResNet-50? <https://blog.roboflow.com/what-is-resnet-50/>.
- [12] Peng Boci et al., *Graph-Retrieval Augmented Generation: A Survey*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.08921>.